

INFLUENCE OF ALPHA – NAPHTHALENE ACETIC ACID (ANAA) ON PANGLOMBOIEN (SYZYGIIUM SPP.) CUTTINGS

Patricio A. Cosep II, Jennifer Lynn C. Teneza, Shierel F. Vallesteros

*College of Forestry, Environment and Resources Management,
Nueva Vizcaya State University- Bayombong Campus,
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11216876>

ABSTRACT

The study evaluated the influence of alpha-naphthalene acetic acid (ANAA) on the Panglomboien cuttings at the different ANAA concentrations. The stem cuttings were put in closed chamber and was being monitored for 38 days. The study used a Completely Randomized Design with four treatments (control, 250 ppm, 750 ppm, 1000 ppm). The result of the study shows a not significant difference among the treatment means. However, among the various concentrations applied, treatment with 250 ppm got the highest result in terms of percent survival, percent callusing, percent rooting, number of roots and root length. Therefore, it is recommended that applying 250 ppm of ANAA is already good enough to the cuttings of Panglomboien and a longer observation for atleast 40-50 days before the data gathering.

Keywords: *Alpha-Naphthalene Acetic Acid (ANAA), Completely Randomized Design, Panglomboien (Syzygium simile)*

INTRODUCTION

Clonal propagation is the process of reproducing genetically-identical plants through asexual means. This is recommended for species that are difficult to propagate due to an irregular supply of their seeds. Clonal propagation could also benefit plant species that are endangered to wild (Sagcal, 2022). Clonal Propagation through tissue culture is popularly known as micropropagation was initiated by G. Morel (1960) who found this as the only commercially viable approach for orchid propagation, since then several crop species have been micropropagated and recipes are now available which can be adopted by growers trained in aseptic manipulation and plant husbandry, clonal propagation 'in vitro' appears to have a permanent advantage in cases in which serious problems with disease occur. This is because of the fact that through 'in vitro' methods more pathogen free plants can be raised and maintained economically. (Kumari, M.2020)

Many native plants naturally propagated vegetatively (that is, without seeds or spores) as a method of ensuring reproduction. Vegetative propagation is commonly found with species that have short seed life, low seed viability, or complex or delayed seed dormancy strategies. Species that inhabit ecosystems with drastic weather patterns, short growing seasons, and endure fires and other disturbances often reproduce vegetatively. All new daughter plants that arise from vegetative propagation are genetically identical to the mother (donor) plant, and these resulting individuals are known as "clones" (Tara, 2009).

Vegetative propagation technique by stem cutting has also been recognized as an effective method of mass propagating exact copies of desirable plants for clonal plantation, reforestation, and commercial purposes (Eirene Grace Z. Arcayos, DOST-PCAARRD S&T Media Services).

According Owen and Lopez (2018) rooting compounds aid in rooting of moderate to difficult-to-root species, accelerate root initiation, improve rooting uniformity, increase the number of roots produced and reduce shrink and rooting time. Alpha-Naphthalene Acetic Acid is a growth hormone used to enhance or regulate growth and development of a plant. It acts as a catalyst for the new roots (halamanin.com).

Based from the study of the University of Florida, University of Kentucky and Texas A&M University, synthetic auxins like IBA and NAA are more commonly used and are more effective.

In this study, Panglomboien is used. *Syzygium simile* is native to the Philippine Island. It can be found to the different places in Luzon, Visayas and Mindanao. This species can grow at forest at low and medium elevation (Pelser, 2009).

Syzygium simile is a small tree up to 15 m tall. Leaves opposite, elliptical-ovate to oblong-ovate, 9-11 cm x 4-6 cm, with c. 14 pairs of fairly indistinct secondary veins, petiole slender, up to 25 mm long. Flowers in panicles from branches below the leaves, calyx c. 3 mm long, with 4 distinct and persistent lobes, petals white. Fruit a subglobose berry, purplish to black (Stuart Jr.,2023).

Research Objective

Generally, the objective of the study is to assess the effect of Alpha-naphthalene acetic acid (ANAA) as rooting substance in Panglomboien tree stem cuttings. Specifically, the objective of the study is to determine if there are significant differences on the number of shoots, length of roots, number of roots, callus and survival.

METHODOLOGY

Location of the study

The study was conducted at the Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Office (PENRO) Nueva Vizcaya Clonal Nursery at Diadi, Nueva Vizcaya. The area was surrounded by tall trees which provide shade to the small plants and structures. During the heat period, it produced a cooling effect and maximized the sultriness of the air. You can find the area with different kinds of seedlings ready to be transplanted. On the other hand, the duration of the study is from October-December 2023.

Figure 01. Location of the study.

Collection and Preparation of Panglomboien Stem Cuttings

A total of 128 cuttings were gathered from the hedge garden of PENRO Nueva Vizcaya Clonal Nursery. The mother trees were observed if it is suitable for collection of cuttings. Based from Atik (1992) it states that choosing a good mother tree entails looking for one that is strong, resilient, bears lots of fruit that is both abundant and healthy, and has good development and form, signifying the goal for which it is being developed. Two nodes' cuttings were obtained from the apical shoot of Panglomboien tree stem. Leaves from the lower part of the cuttings were removed and the remaining leaves were trimmed into half to minimize transpiration. The collected stem cuttings were placed in a pail with water to avoid desiccation and to wash off dusts and later was soaked in Manzate fungicides for a minute.

Figure 2. Source of Cuttings of Panglomboien located at the Clonal Nursery area in Diadi, Nueva Vizcaya

Preparation of Rooting Substances

In this study, Alpha- Naphthalene Acetic Acid (ANAA) as rooting substance was used to evaluate the rooting performance of stem cuttings. Treatments and the corresponding amounts used as follow;

Table 01. Treatment and Descriptions

Treatments	Particulars
T1	Distilled water/ 40 ml
T2	250 ppm
T3	750 ppm
T4	1000 ppm

Figure 03. Soaking of cuttings

Planting of Panglomboien Stem Cuttings

The bundled stem cuttings were soaked in the containers with rooting substances. Treated stem cuttings were planted in the clonal chamber filled with sand as rooting media and watered it using hand sprinkler.

Maintenance of Cuttings

The planted Panglomboien stem cuttings were placed in a transparent clonal chamber to ensure proper maintenance. Labeling each treatment was necessary to

facilitate better monitoring and watering of planted stem cuttings was done, if necessary, also fallen leaves was removed to avoid pathological factors that will affect the cuttings.

Experimental Design and Lay-out

The study was laid out in Completely Randomized Design (CRD). There were 8 cuttings per replicates, replicated four times. Randomization was done using draw lots and it was presented below:

T1R4	T3R1	T4R4	T3R4
T3R3	T4R3	T1R3	T4R2
T2R1	T3R2	T4R1	T2R3
T1R2	T2R4	T2R2	T1R1

Figure 2. Lay out plan using Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four treatments, replicated four times

Legend:

T1- Treatment 1

T2- Treatment 2

T3- Treatment 3

T4- Treatment 4

R1- Replication 1

R2- Replication 2

R3- Replication 3

R4- Replication 4

Data Collection

The observations of the parameters were done 38 days after the emergence of roots and shoots. All the cuttings were taken out from the chamber carefully to prevent the stress of the cuttings and to check carefully the roots and callus, the roots are being submerged to water to wash-out the soil that adhere from the roots.

To determine the percent survival in each treatment, the number of cuttings with shoot and root were counted and recorded. The percent survival was computed as follows:

$$\% \text{ Survival} = \frac{\text{Number of cuttings with shoot and root}}{\text{Total number of cuttings planted}} \times 100$$

For the number of roots especially the adventitious root, and number of shoots, this were counted per cuttings.

Meanwhile, for percent callusing, this formula was being used.

$$\% \text{ Callusing} = \frac{\text{Number of cuttings with callus but no roots and shoots}}{\text{Total number of cuttings planted}} \times 100$$

On the other hand, assessment of the rooting performance of Panglomboien tree stem cuttings using ANAA as rooting substances was evaluated based on number of shoots, length of root, number of roots, callus and survival as parameters. In terms of the length of root, the primary root was measured using a ruler in centimeters starting from the point to the tip of the root.

Data Analysis

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to evaluate the significance of the treatments together with Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research (STAR) software package to further test the significance between or among the treatment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A cutting of Panglomboien from the stem cuttings were used to determine the effect of Alpha-Napthalene Acetic Acid (ANAA) as a rooting substance. Vegetative propagation of Panglomboien cutting was evaluated using the parameters; root length, number of shoots, number of roots, percent rooting, percent shooting, percent callusing, percent survival.

Root length

In the length of the primary root, the result shows that treatment 2 (250 ppm) has the highest number of root length, followed by treatment 4 (1000 ppm), treatment 3 (750 ppm) and treatment 1 (control) respectively.

Figure 04. Root length data of Panglomboien.

Based from the record of the study, it was in treatment 1 were there is a record of longest root length which is 4.9 centimeters. However, it shows in the result that even though treatment 1 recorded the longest root, it is still the lowest in terms of root length. This is in contradict in the study of Dolkas (2021), where it states that bottled spring water or well water works best, due to higher levels of minerals. Furthermore, treatment 2 has recorded the highest number of root length and it shows that Alpha-Naphthalene Acetic Acid (ANAA) has an effect on it as supported from the study of Gonzales (2018) on the influence of alpha-naphthalence acetic acid (ANAA) on Lubeg cuttings where the results showed a significant effect on different ANAA concentrations on callus formation and length of roots.

Number of shoots

In the number of shoots, the result indicated a not significant difference in number between treatments. Treatment 3 (750 ppm) has the highest number of shoots, followed by treatment 4 (1000 ppm), treatment 2 (250 ppm), and treatment 1 (control) respectively.

Figure 05. Number of shoot data of Panglomboien.

In this study, it was observed that Panglomboien has a single shoot per cuttings and it was found mostly on the tip of the cuttings. Likewise, it was also observed that the shoots are very sensitive to wilting and stress.

One factor in shoot development is light. According to Tombesi et al. (2015), in greenhouses, light intensity, the main driver of leaf photosynthesis should generally keep low to limit leaf transpiration and heating. Pan et al. (2021), stated also that high temperature increases leaf transpiration leading to wilting.

Number of roots

It was shown in the result that Treatment 2 (250 ppm) has the highest number of roots, the same from the root length (see figure 04) followed by treatment 4, treatment 3 and treatment 1 respectively. It also shows that there is no significant effect between the number of roots and treatments.

Figure 06. Number of roots data of Panglomboien.

The highest number of roots were observed in treatment 2 with 250 ppm of Alpha-Naphthalene Acetic Acid (ANAA). For the number of roots, this was evaluated by directly counting the roots per cuttings. There is no significant effect between the number of roots and treatments, this is also the same on the study of Gonzales (2018), where in her study on Lubeg, there is no significant effect on different Alpha-Naphthalene Acetic Acid (ANAA) concentrations on root initiation, number of roots and survival rate. However, in the study of Hossain and Urbi (2015), the results of their study showed that different concentrations of NAA significantly affected the rooting characteristics of *A. paniculata* and 2.5 mM of NAA was found to be more effective to induce rooting in young apical shoot (YAS) cuttings compared to other concentrations and old apical shoot (OAS). This study also postulates that adventitious rooting response depends on the juvenility of plant material and concentration of growth regulator.

Percent rooting

The percent rooting of Panglomboien tree stem cuttings was not mainly affected by the ANAA as a rooting substance. Although treatment 2 has the highest percent rooting with a 58.6 % followed by Treatment 4 with a 55.47 %. While treatment 3 and 2 has the lowest percent rooting with 50 % and 39.84 % respectively.

Figure 07. Percent rooting data of Panglomboien.

Percent shooting

Analysis on the percent shooting of Panglomboien tree stem cuttings after 60 days, revealed a not significant differences on the treatment applied. The figure below shows that T3 has the highest percent shooting with 18.75 % followed by T4 and T2 with 17.18 % and 13.28% respectively. While T1 has the lowest percent rooting with 10.16 %

Figure. 08. Percent shooting data of Panglomboien.

Percent callusing

Based from the figure below, Treatment 2 has the highest number of percent callusing with 14.84 % followed by treatment 4 and 1 with 14.84% and 11.72 % respectively. While treatment 3 has the lowest number of calluses with 9.38 %.

Figure. 09 Percent callusing data of Panglomboien.

. “Callus” in the early days of plant biology referred to the massive growth of cells and accumulation of callose associated with wounding (Robins and Hervey, 1970). Furthermore, according to the study of Patricio (2004), a callus is a type of wound tissue that covers a cut on the stem and cover exposed wood by developing as an amorphous mass with bigger and looser arrangement of parenchyma cells. Plants develop unorganized cell masses like callus and tumors in response to various biotic and abiotic stimuli (Ikeuchi, Sugimoto, and Iwase, 2013).

Percent survival

Based from the study, the analysis of percent survival of Panglomboien tree after 38 days revealed that there is no significant difference between the treatments. It shows that treatment 2 has the highest survival rate with 20.31 % survival followed by treatment 4 with 19.53 % survival rate. While treatment 3 and 1 has the lowest the same survival rate with 18 and 18.75 percent. From a total of 128 cuttings there is 76.59 % percent survival rate based from the total average per treatment.

Figure 10. Percent survival of Panglomboien

Boretti and Florentine (2019), stated that there are primary factors affecting the plant or cutting growth includes sunlight, water, temperature and nutrients. Lack of water has always been a detrimental factor preventing plant survival. Another is the poor aeration in waterlogged conditions that leads to the decay of cuttings before root initiation. According to Kester (1970) as cited by Owen and Maynard (2007), temperature and light are two key environmental components that determine rooting success. Maintaining lower air temperature reduces shoot or stem temperature. This in turn, reduces the rate of shoot and leaf growth that could deplete carbohydrate reserves and desiccate propagule.

In order a cutting to survive and form roots, it must be able to maintain a healthy water balance and replenish water in transpiration (Patricio, 2004).

Table 02. Summary on the analysis of variance for Panglomboien cuttings. (*Syzigium simile*)

Parameters	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Root length	0.36	Not Significant
Number of Shoot	0.16	Not Significant
Number of roots	0.64	Not Significant
Percent rooting	0.36	Not Significant
Percent Shooting	0.45	Not Significant
Percent callusing	0.52	Not Significant
Percent Survival	0.78	Not Significant

Table shows that among the parameters, it shows a not significant difference since the p-value was greater than 5% level of significance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based from the result of the study, the researchers found out that Alpha-Naphthalene Acetic Acid has a considerable effect on the Panglomboien cuttings. It shows that Panglomboien can grow directly even without the application of ANAA. While on the other hand, it was found out that the Panglomboien cuttings has higher percent survival rate on treatment 2 with 250 ppm of Alpha-Naphthalene Acetic Acid (ANAA) likewise with percent callusing, percent rooting, number of roots and root length. Therefore, the researchers recommend, that applying 250 ppm of Alpa-Naphthalene Acetic Acid is good enough for the cuttings of Panglomboien. Furthermore, in order to gather more significant data, it is recommended that atleast 40-50 days' time allotment before the data gathering and based from the clonal experts from the Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Office (PENRO) Nueva Vizcaya Clonal Nursery, they suggested that the best time to do cloning or vegetative propagations is during the summer season.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to acknowledge the assistance of the Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Office (PENRO) - Clonal propagation area of the Province of Nueva Vizcaya.

REFERENCES

- Dolkas, P. (2021). Rooting Plants in Water: The Easiest Way to Bring Greenery Indoors. Retrieved from. www.mydomaine.com
- Hossain Md. S., & Urbi Z. (2016). Effect of Naphthalene Acetic Acid on the Adventitious Rooting in Shoot Cuttings of *Andrographis paniculata* (Burm.f.) Wall. ex Nees: An Important Therapeutical Herb. International Journal of Agronomy. Retrieved from <https://www.hindawi.com/journals/ija/2016/1617543/>.
- Gonzales A. (2018). Influence of alpha-naphthalene acetic acid (ANAA) on lubeg (Syzgium spp.) marcots. JBES. Volume 12. N5. May. p283-291.
- Ikeuchi M., Sugimoto, K., Iwase, A. (2013). Plant Callus: Mechanisms of Induction and Repression. *The Plant Cell*, 25 (9), pp. 3159–3173. DOI: 10.1105/tpc.113.116053
- Kumari M. (2020). Botany Lectures. Clonal Propagation. Retrieved from. <http://anccpatna.ac.in/departments/botany/lectures/PGSem-II/ClonalPropagationforM.Sc.Sem20IIBotany>
- Luna T. (2009). Vegetative propagation. In: Dumroese, R. Kasten; Luna, Tara; Landis, Thomas D., editors. Nursery manual for native plants: A guide for tribal nurseries - Volume 1: Nursery management. Agriculture Handbook 730. Washington, D.C.: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service. p. 153-175.
- Owen W.G. and Lopez R. (2018). Rooting Hormones improve uniformity among vegetative cuttings. Michigan State University Extension. Department of Horticulture

- Pan T, Chen X-l, Hao Y-p, Jiang C-w, Wang S, Wang J-s, et al. (2021) Optimization of factors affecting the rooting of pine wilt disease resistant Masson pine (*Pinus massoniana*) stem cuttings. PLoS ONE 16(9): e0251937. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0251937>
- Patricio, H.P. (2004). Effect of different rooting media and level of indolebutyric acid (IBA) on macropropagated Guijo (*Shorea guiso*) stem cutting. Unpublished masteral thesis. Nueva Vizcaya State University.
- Pelser, P.B., Barcelona J.F., and Nickrent D.L. (2011). Co's Digital Flora of the Philippines. Retrieved from; www.philippineplants.org.
- Sagcal, J. (2022). Clonal propagation: what it is and how it is done. Retrieved from agriculture.com.ph.
- Stuart Jr, G. (2023). Philippine Medicinal Plants:Panglomboien. StuartXchange.com.
- Tara L. (2009). Vegetative Propagation. Nursery Manual for Native Plants; A guide for tribal nurseries. Volume 1 Nursery Management. United States Department of Agriculture and Forest Services. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com.ph/books?id=PI3GHMWD1-sC&pg=PA153&lpg=PA153&dq>.
- Tombesi, S., Palliotti A., Poni S., and Farinelli D. (2015). Influence of light and shoot development stage leaf photosynthesis and carbohydrate status during the adventitious root formation in cutting of *Corylus avellana* L. National center for Biotechnology Information. National Library of Medicine. DOI.org/10.3389/fpls.2015.00973
- University of Florida, University of Kentucky, Texas A&M University. (2023). Auxin. Department of Environmental horticulture, Institute of food and Agricultural Sciences.

Webpage with no Author

<https://agriculture.com.ph/2022/05/21/dost-pcaarrd-visits-native-forest-and-clonally-propagated-tree-species-in-qsu/>